
Punctuation Errors Made by Elementary Level Students in the Middle East Context in General and Oman in Particular

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Abstract

Error is inevitably committed by learners while learning anything and it is too obvious while learning a new language. Identifying errors in their writing is unquestionably an essential part of language learning. Finding errors is an essential step for learning problem areas of the learners in the target language. Knowing these kinds of errors help teachers in the teaching and learning process, creating remedial material and finally in syllabus designing. It is necessary for the teachers to be aware of the errors repeatedly made by learners, their types and reasons for those errors.

Keywords: Error, mother tongue interference (MTI), punctuation, interlingual errors, capitalization, comma, full stop.

Introduction

The present paper is an analysis of the errors in using punctuation marks by the students of intermediate level. How listening skill is incomplete without proper speaking skill, same is the case with writing skill; reading skill is incomplete without proper writing skill, if a writer fails to use appropriate symbols and signs in suitable places. So it becomes very difficult for a reader to understand what the writer wants to say. Therefore, four skills of English language are very important and they integrate one another. Since, speaking and writing are productive skills; they play a vital role in the life of students when it comes for examinations. It was observed that students of intermediate level do errors in some punctuation marks. Like in other languages, punctuation marks are important mechanics of writing in English where the message is misunderstood if these signs and symbols are not used suitably.

The students at intermediate level write different kinds of write-ups like paragraphs, and email writing. Due to using improper punctuation marks, students cannot get good grades in writing skill. The current research is very useful for students and teachers as well

since it helps to find out what kind of errors students make, and reasons behind them. This study tries to highlight the exclusivity of the Middle East context in general and Oman in particular in analyzing the errors made by the students.

Objectives:

- To identify the common errors by the students in using punctuation marks like capital letter, comma and full stop
- To discover the reasons for making these errors
- To find out whether MT has any influence in making these errors

Study Questions:

- What are the common punctuation errors done by the intermediate level students?
- What are the probable reasons behind making such kind of errors in their writing?
- How to help the students to minimize the errors in using capital letter, comma and full stop?

Literature Review

There is sufficient research done on how the learners learn first and second languages and it shows that there are differences in the way learners use different approaches in learning the spelling and punctuation of any language that learners acquire. The native speakers of any language usually establish spelling and pronunciation patterns of words. As a

result, speakers gradually develop their own linguistic instincts.

However, this pattern formation goes through many developmental stages and requires multiple encounters with language. In this process, the speaker hears sounds and builds hypotheses about their usage, tests these hypotheses on the input they receive and when they communicate using language, but knowledge of the spelling structure of words is primarily relevant for native speakers of all suggestive languages. This means that native speakers can usually spell or utter a word without knowing exactly the rules behind its spelling and pronunciation. They believe that they can learn words by drawing and find them in communication without paying much attention to how they are made. Furthermore, evidences suggest that children spell words by recognizing pronunciation in the early stages of language acquisition, and then go on to study morpheme-grapheme correspondences as they begin to read and write (Hayes et al., 2006).

Some of the scholars mentioned the importance of punctuation in writing and it can be understood from the following.

“The benefits of learning good grammar are many and varied, from ability to express spoken thoughts effectively to improved understanding of the written word and better writing skills.” (Mary et al., 2001)

“The very word, grammar, probably calls up bad memories of being the last person in your 6th grade class to understand what subordinate clause means. But the truth is the basic terminology and concepts of grammar aren't all that hard to master and understanding them is the surest route to eliminate common grammatical errors from your speech.” (Batko, 2004)

“All the writing requires complete mastery of punctuation because it is punctuation which removes ambiguities and makes prose clear and easily comprehensible.” (Rehman, 2005)

“Punctuation is a device used by a writer to help his readers understand the meaning of his words.” (Rehman, 2005)

“Punctuation clarifies the meaning of the written sentence.” (Mary et al., 2001)

“Speakers divide their messages into chunks called information units..... Readers of a written text, however, interpret what they read by mentally assigning information units to the text, helped by punctuation and the grammar.” (Downing, 2015)

Research methodology

This study deals with punctuation marks. Restricted by Error Analysis; the researchers used the error analysis steps suggested by Rod Ellis in 1994. The subjects of this study were students at one of the colleges of Technology. A random

sample size of 50 was selected from the writings of Intermediate level students. Researchers identified errors from data obtained from the sources. Then, as mentioned above, the errors are described according to their type, i.e. misuse of commas, capitalization and full stop. The researchers explained the errors and tried to evaluate and correct them by citing the use of various authentic references to English punctuation. Only the errors discussed in the results here perfectly represent the usage pattern. Since this study only includes intermediate level students, the errors discussed in this study were at the intermediate level. It was observed that the students were neither able nor considered to be proficient in using English fluently to avoid making mistakes at the advanced level.

Findings

The researchers of the present study carried out the research and observed a few errors in the use of capitalization, comma, and full stop or a period, which are explained in detail with examples under each heading. Each subsection gives the details of usage and purposes of each mark of the study and presents the errors from the written scripts of the subjects with corrections. The following table shows the types of errors and their division in each type. In total, for the present study, 244 were errors found from the written scripts of the students.

Error Type	unnecessary insertion (Error %)	omission (Error %)	wrong choice (Error %)	Total
capital letters	66 (44)	84 (56)	---	150
comma	3 (4.75)	57 (89)	4 (6.25)	64
full stop	1 (3.33)	20 (66.66)	9 (30)	30
Total	70	161	13	244

Error analysis in the use of capital letter

The Cambridge dictionary identifies 'capital letter' as one of the punctuation marks in English (Cambridge Dictionary, 2023). Capital letter can be used for different purposes like:

- to mark the beginning of a sentence
- at the beginning of proper nouns of people, places, countries, firms, nationalities, languages, mountains, seas, oceans, titles, headings, abbreviations, and acronyms
- for the titles of the books, magazines and newspapers, plays, and music
- at the beginning of the names of days, months, and holidays
- at the beginning of quoted sentences

It was identified that 150 errors were made by the students in the usage of capital letters. The errors of capitalization done by the subjects of the study can be divided into two: omission of capital and unnecessary use of capital. They are explained in detail below.

Omission (Error %)	Unnecessary insertion (Error %)	Total
84 (56%)	66 (44%)	150

Omission of capital letter:

The first category of error in capitalisation is Omission of capital letter where it is supposed to be used. There were 84 errors identified in the written scripts and they amount 56% of the errors.

Here are a few examples from the students' scripts:

Written Error	Correction
in the end ...	In the end ...
than I go to ...	Then, I go to ...
. after that, ...	After that, ...
I like when i back from college do something.	When I come back from college, I like doing ...

Unnecessary use of capital letter:

The second category of error in capitalization is unnecessary use of capital letter where it is not supposed to be used. There were 66 errors found in the written scripts of the students and they amount to 44% of the total errors of capitalisation.

Here are a few examples from the students' scripts:

Written Error	Correction
I like going To the library...	I like going to the library...
I love All people ...	I love all people ...
... most of the T ime, the most of the t ime, the ...
... in the N ext morning.	... in the n ext morning.

Error analysis in the use of comma (,)

In writing, the comma is one of the mostly used punctuation marks. Here are the basic uses of comma (Cambridge Dictionary, 2023):

- To separate the independent clauses where for, and, nor, but, or, yet, and so ("fanboys") are used
- After an introductory clause or phrase
- With three or more words of same series used without a conjunction
- To set off appositives
- With a noun to indicate direct address
- With dates, titles, numbers and addresses
- To set off a question tag
- To start direct quotations

It was found that 64 errors were made by the students in the usage of comma. They can be divided into three categories such as: error by omission, error by unnecessary insertion, and error by wrong choice. They are explained in detail below.

Omission (Error %)	Unnecessary insertion (Error %)	Wrong choice (Error %)	Total
3 (4.75)	57 (89)	4 (6.25)	64

The first category of errors is omission of comma where it is supposed to be used. There were 57 errors found in the written scripts and they amount 89% of the errors. Here are a few examples from the students' scripts:

a. **Written sentence:** Finally I don't like any things that better.

Corrected sentence: Finally, I don't like anything that bothers me.

b. **Written sentence:** When I am reading I feeling happy and of course the reading make the people smart...

Corrected sentence: When I am reading, I feel happy and of course, the reading makes people smart...

c. **Written sentence:** I like college building because it is a big and modern.

Corrected sentence: I like the college building, because it is very big and modern.

Another category of errors is unnecessary use of comma. There were 3 errors found and they amount 4.7% of the total errors in comma. Here is an example:

Part of the written sentence: ... with a group study, a very quiet place ...

Correction part: ... with a group study, in a very quiet place ...

And the final category of error is wrong choice of comma in the sentences. There were 4 errors and they amount 6.25% of the errors and here is an example from a student's script:

Part of the written sentence: ... things that likes,

Correction part: ... things that I like.

Error analysis in the use of full stop or period (.)

Full stop is the term used in British English (Br E) and it is known as a period in American English (Am E). Full stop or period can be used in some of the places such as:

- at the end of a complete sentence which is a statement, but not a question or an exclamation
- at the end of a group of words, which are not structured conventionally
- at the end of a command or a suggestion

- at the end of an indirect question
- in some abbreviations
- in emails and website addresses

It was found that 30 errors were made by the students in the usage of full stop. They can be divided into three categories such as: error by omission, error by unnecessary insertion, and error by wrong choice. They are explained in detail below.

unnecessary insertion (Error %)	omission (Error %)	wrong choice (Error %)	Total
1 (3.33)	20 (66.66)	9 (30)	30

The first category of errors is omission of full stop where it is supposed to be used. There were 20 errors found in the written scripts and they amount 66.66% of the errors. Here are a few examples from the students' scripts:

Part of the written sentence:... write this email to you

Corrected part:... write this email to you.

Part of the written sentence: ... like and dis like

Corrected part:... like and dislike.

Next category of errors is unnecessary use of a full stop. There was 1 error found

and it amounts 3.33% of the total errors in a full stop. Here is the example:

Part of the written sentence:... to know the animals from near. And watch ...

Corrected part:... to know the animals from near and watch ...

And the final category of error is wrong choice of a full stop in the sentences. There were 9 errors and they amount 30% of the errors and here is an example:

Part of the written sentence: How are you and your family.

Corrected part: How are you and your family?

Delimitations of the Study:

Though there are many punctuation marks in total, due to the limitations like lack of time, the researchers have restricted the study to find out the common punctuation errors made by the students while using capital letter comma and full stop.

Discussion and Conclusion

These are some of the punctuation errors done by intermediate level students in their writing. As a result of the study, it can be clearly seen that these errors like capitalization, comma, and full stop can be traced to the interference of learners' first language. When it comes to the learners' first language which is Arabic, there is no capitalization and the punctuation conventions of English language are different from Arabic language. It is suggested that in order to avoid L1 interference, Arabic EFL students should be taught punctuation marks explicitly and capitalisation and periods particularly.

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